

SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status

Emanuele Simioni¹, Michele Zusi², Romolo Politi²,
Fabrizio Capaccioni², Cristina Re¹, Alain Doressoundiram³, Pasquale Palumbo², Mathieu
Vincendon⁴, Gabriele Cremonese¹

¹INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo Osservatorio 5,35122, Padua, Italy

²INAF- Istituto Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

³Observatoire de Paris – PLS, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique (LESIA), 92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale, CNRS / Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

Index

INDEX	2
1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1. SCOPE	4
1.2. REFERENCE DOCUMENT	4
1.3. ACRONYMS	4
1.4. DOCUMENT FORMAT AND REPOSITORY	5
1.5. DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION	5
2. FOP ORGANIZATION	6
2.1. TC SEQUENCES	6
3. TC ORGANIZATION	7
3.1. TC DEFINITION	7
3.1.1. <i>Spacecraft TCs</i>	8
3.1.2. <i>ME TCs</i>	10
3.1.3. <i>HRIC TCs</i>	11
3.1.4. <i>STC TCs</i>	13
3.1.5. <i>VIHI TCs</i>	15
3.2. TC RANGE (VSS) DEFINITION	17
3.3. TC CALIBRATIONS	20
3.3.1. <i>TC Numerical Calibrations (CSSP)</i>	20
3.3.2. <i>TC Textual Calibrations (CSSP)</i>	22
4. TM ORGANIZATION	25
4.1. TM DEFINITION	25
4.2. TM CALIBRATION	28
4.2.1. <i>TM Numerical Calibration (CSSP)</i>	28
4.2.2. <i>Textual Calibrations (CSST)</i>	29
4.3. TM OUT OF LIMITS	32

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

Approval

Edited by:	Emanuele Simioni
	Michele Zusi
Revised by:	Gabriele Cremonese
Approved by:	Gabriele Cremonese

Document Change Record

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

In this document we will describe the Telemetry and Telecommands completeness status for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS).

1.2. Reference Document

[RD. 1] BC-SIM-TN-003 - Reports and Note Layout and Flow - Version 2

[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)

[RD. 2] MIB report 20170913 – AIRBUS BepiColombo Database Extract TC Packet Overview

1.3. Acronyms

APID	Application Process IDentifier
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FOP	Flight Operation Plan.
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
PDS	Planetary Data System
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
ROI	Region of Interest
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM
SSC	Source Sequence Count
STC	STEReo imaging Channel
TC	Telecommand
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

XML eXtensible Markup Language

1.4. Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow **[RD. 1]** and will be archived both on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5. Document Organization

As depicted in Table 1, Section 2 will describe FOP defined until now and the TCs involved

Section 3.1 the Telecommand (TC) Sequences together with their parameters.

Section 3.3 will report each TCs including the calibration curve (numeric or textual) and the range of limits.

Section 4 will report each Telemetry (TM) including the calibration curve (numeric or textual) and Out of Limits.

Next table summarizes the Sections for a better use of the document.

Table 1 Table of the contents following the document organization and reporting the hyperlink to the Sections.

Main Parameter	SubType	Sub-Section	Section
FOP	Organization		<u>2</u>
TC	Organization		<u>3.1</u>
		Spacecraft	<u>3.1.1</u>
		ME	<u>3.1.2</u>
		HRIC	<u>3.1.3</u>
		STC	<u>3.1.4</u>
	VIHI	<u>3.1.5</u>	
	Range definition		<u>3.2</u>
	TC Calibration		<u>3.3</u>
		Numerical Calibration	<u>3.3.1</u>
		Textual Calibration	<u>3.3.2</u>
TM	Organization		<u>4</u>
	TM Calibration		<u>4.2</u>
		Numerical Calibration	<u>4.2.1</u>
		Textual Calibration	<u>4.2.2</u>
	TM Out of Limits		<u>4.3</u>

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

2. FOP Organization

2.1. TC Sequences

This section will list for each SIMBIO-SYS Sequence the TCs used and their parameters. A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 2 Link to the complete report of the Sequences structure

DB1_1_TC sequence structure.xlsx	
----------------------------------	---

The table reports the description, the TCs involved , the timing, the parameters involved in each TC and their value (if not formal) for each Sequence.

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

3. TC Organization

The following sub-sections will report the current ESOC database for what concern the SIMBIO-SYS TCs (see Section 3.1), including:

- their parameters
- their calibration, both in the case of numeric (see Section 3.3.1) and textual (see Section 3.3.2)
- their limiting ranges (see Section 3.2).

3.1. TC definition

This section will list for each SIMBIO-SYS TCs the parameters involved. A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 3 Link to the complete report of the TCs

DB1_2_ZSS_TC packets and structure.xlsx	
---	---

The next tables reports the description, the parameters involved and for each parameter for each TC:

- The parameter name and description
- The parameter bit position and length
- ID of the calibration of the parameter (for the numerical see Section 3.3.1, for the textual see Section 3.3.2)
- the ID of the ranges of the parameters (for details see Section 3.2).
-

Telecommands are divided as follows:

Subdivision	Section	Table	Type	Range
SpaceCraft TCs	3.1.1	Table 4	ZSSK	4000 - 4008
ME TCs	3.1.2	Table 5	ZSS	305 - 17007
HRIC TCs	3.1.3	Table 6	ZSS	17101 - 17121
STC TCs	3.1.4	Table 7	ZSS	17201 - 17221
VIHI TCs	3.1.5	Table 8 Error! Reference source not found.	ZSS	17301 - 17321

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

3.1.1. Spacecraft TCs

Table 4 Limited report of the Spacecraft TCs (ZSSK).

Name	Descr.	PARA NAME	Description	bit-position	bit length	Calibration	Range
ZSSK4000	Start OBCP: SIMBIO ME Switch On	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
		PKK00011	OBCP Param ID 1	88	32		
		PKK00021	Nominal Redundant	120	8	CKKT0004TC	
		PKK00012	OBCP Param ID 2	128	32		
		PKK00102	ASW Start	160	8	CKKT0029TC	
		PKK00013	OBCP Param ID 3	168	32		
		PKK000103	EEPROM_START_ADDRESS	200	32		
		PKK00014	OBCP Param ID 4	232	32		
		PKK00104	IMG_LENGTH	264	32		
		PKK00015	OBCP Param ID 5	296	32		
ZSSK4001	Start OBCP: SIMBIO ME Switch Off	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
ZSSK4002	Start OBCP: SIMBIO HRIC Switch On	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
		PKK00011	OBCP Param ID 1	88	32		
ZSSK4003	Start OBCP: SIMBIO STC Switch On	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
		PKK00011	OBCP Param ID 1	88	32		
ZSSK4004	Start OBCP: SIMBIO VIHI Switch On	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
		PKK00011	OBCP Param ID 1	88	32		
ZSSK4005	Start OBCP: SIMBIO HRIC Graceful Shutdown	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
ZSSK4006	Start OBCP: SIMBIO STC Graceful Shutdown	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
ZSSK4007	Start OBCP: SIMBIO VIHI Graceful Shutdown	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	
		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
ZSSK4008	Start OBCP: SIMBIO Emergency Switch Off	PKK00001	OBCP Identifier	0	32		
		PKK00002	Emergency Flag	32	1	CKKT0001TC	

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		PKK00003	NS	72	16		
		PKK00011	OBCP Param ID 1	88	32		
		PKK00093	Shutdown	120	8	CKKT0022TC	

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

3.1.2. ME TCs

Table 5 Limited report from ME TC.

Name	Descr.	PARA NAME	Description	bit- pos- ition	bit s len- gth	Calibration	Range
ZSS00305	SIMB Enable HK Para Report Generation	PSS08003	SID	0	8	CSST0002TC	
ZSS00306	SIMB Disable HK Para Report Generation	PSS08003	SID	0	8	CSST0002TC	
ZSS00329	SIMB Define HK Report Collect Interval	PSS08003	SID	0	8	CSST0002TC	
		PSS08004	Collection Interval	8	16		VSS08004
ZSS00602	SIMB Load Data in Memory	PSS06060	Memory ID	0	16	CSST6060TC	CSS06060TC
		PSS06065	Start Address	16	32		
		PSS06066	Length of Load Block	48	32		
		PSS06069	Data Word	80	32		
ZSSY0602	SIMB Load Data in Memory (OBSM)	PSS06060	Memory ID	0	16	CSST6060TC	CSS06060TC
		PSS06065	Start Address	16	32		
		PSS06066	Length of Load Block	48	32		
		PSSY6069	Data Word	80	0		
ZSS00605	SIMB Dump Memory Area	PSS06060	Memory ID	0	16	CSST6060TC	CSS06060TC
		PSS06065	Start Address	16	32		
		PSS06067	Length of Dump Block	48	32		
ZSS00609	SIMB Check Memory Area	PSS06060	Memory ID	0	16	CSST6060TC	CSS06060TC
		PSS06065	Start Address	16	32		
		PSS06068	num of bytes to check	48	32		
ZSS00929	SIMB Accept Time Update	PSS08917	On_Board Time	0	48		
ZSS01701	SIMB Perform Connection Test						
ZSS01728	SIMB Test TC max Length	PSS17128	N for TC with max length	0	8		
		PSS17129	Data for TC with max len	8	8		
ZSS02101	SIMB Enable Start Science Transfer	PSS08005	PID	0	8		VSS08005
ZSS02102	SIMB Disable Stop Science Transfer	PSS08005	PID	0	8		VSS08005
ZSS02128	SIMB Reset Output Buffer						
ZSS17001	SIMB START_ASW	PSS03201	address of image in RAM	0	32		
ZSS17002	SIMB Memory RAM Image consistency Check	PSS03201	address of image in RAM	0	32		
		PSS03202	Length of Image	32	32		
		PSS03203	CRC value	64	16		
ZSS17003	SIMB EEPROM Memory Copy	PSS03205	address of image in EEPR	0	32		
		PSS03202	Length of Image	32	32		
		PSS03206	Destination addr in RAM	64	32		
ZSS17004	SIMB ASW upload in EEPROM	PSS03201	address of image in RAM	0	32		
		PSS03202	Length of Image	32	32		
		PSS03204	Destination address EEPR	64	32		
ZSS17005	SIMB Start ME Diagnostic Mode						
ZSS17006	SIMB Stop ME Diagnostic Mode						
ZSS17007	SIMB ME gracefull shutdown						

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

3.1.3. HRIC TCs

Table 6 Limited report for HRIC TCs.

Name	Descr.	PARA NAME	Description	bit-position	bit length	Calibration	Range
ZSS17101	SIMB HRIC power On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17102	SIMB HRIC SCIENCE	PSS01501	integration time	0	16	CSSP0001TC	
		PSS01601	repetition time HRIC	16	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01601
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	32	16		VSS01602
		PSS00202	binning factor w2	48	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00201	binning factor w1	50	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00301	number of windows	53	3		VSS03001
		PSS00204	binning factor w4	60	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00203	binning factor w3	62	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	64	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	75	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	80	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	91	5		VSS00502
		PSS01103	start row pixel w2	96	11		VSS01101
		PSS00503	start strip pixel w2	107	5		VSS00501
		PSS01104	end row pixel w2	112	11		VSS01102
		PSS00504	end strip pixel w2	123	5		VSS00502
		PSS01105	start row pixel w3	128	11		VSS01101
		PSS00505	start strip pixel w3	139	5		VSS00501
		PSS01106	end row pixel w3	144	11		VSS01102
		PSS00506	end strip pixel w3	155	5		VSS00502
		PSS01107	start row pixel w4	160	11		VSS01102
		PSS00507	start strip pixel w4	171	5		VSS00501
		PSS01108	end row pixel w4	176	11		VSS01102
		PSS00508	end strip pixel w4	187	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimensio	192	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	194	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00602	Compression ratio w2	202	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00603	Compression ratio w3	210	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00604	Compression ratio w4	218	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	231	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	240	8		VSS08008
ZSS171B2	SIMB HRIC SCIENCE 1ms	PSS015B1	integration time 1ms	0	16	CSSP0002TC	VSS01618
		PSS01601	repetition time HRIC	16	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01601
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	32	16		VSS01602
		PSS00202	binning factor w2	48	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00201	binning factor w1	50	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00301	number of windows	53	3		VSS03001
		PSS00204	binning factor w4	60	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS00203	binning factor w3	62	2	CSST0004TC	VSS00201
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	64	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	75	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	80	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	91	5		VSS00502
		PSS01103	start row pixel w2	96	11		VSS01101
		PSS00503	start strip pixel w2	107	5		VSS00501
		PSS01104	end row pixel w2	112	11		VSS01102
		PSS00504	end strip pixel w2	123	5		VSS00502

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		PSS01105	start row pixel w3	128	11		VSS01101
		PSS00505	start strip pixel w3	139	5		VSS00501
		PSS01106	end row pixel w3	144	11		VSS01102
		PSS00506	end strip pixel w3	155	5		VSS00502
		PSS01107	start row pixel w4	160	11		VSS01102
		PSS00507	start strip pixel w4	171	5		VSS00501
		PSS01108	end row pixel w4	176	11		VSS01102
		PSS00508	end strip pixel w4	187	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimensio	192	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	194	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00602	Compression ratio w2	202	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00603	Compression ratio w3	210	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00604	Compression ratio w4	218	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	231	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	240	8		VSS08008
ZSS17103	SIMB HRIC Thermal Control On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
		PSS01603	STC HRIC Temp set point	8	16		VSS01614
ZSS17104	SIMB HRIC Confirm Command						
ZSS17105	SIMB HRIC Upload parameters	PSS08007	HRIC param ID	0	8	CSST0013TC	VSS08007
		PSS01604	parameter value	8	32		
ZSS17106	SIMB HRIC Read Addr	PSS01605	PE HRIC Addr	0	16	CSST0012TC	VSS01604
ZSS17107	SIMB HRIC Write Addr	PSS01605	PE HRIC Addr	0	16	CSST0012TC	VSS01604
		PSS01606	Value to be write	16	16		
ZSS17108	SIMB HRIC Test PE	PSS01608	Word 0-1	0	16		VSS01607
		PSS01609	Word 2-3	16	16		VSS01607
		PSS01610	Word 4-5	32	16		VSS01607
		PSS01611	Word 6-7	48	16		VSS01607
		PSS01612	Word 8-9	64	16		VSS01607
		PSS01613	Word 10-11	80	16		VSS01607
		PSS01614	Word 12-13	96	16		VSS01607
		PSS01615	Word 14-15	112	16		VSS01607
		PSS01616	Word 16-17	128	16		VSS01607
		PSS01617	Word 18-19	144	16		VSS01607
		PSS01618	Word 20-21	160	16		VSS01607
		PSS01619	Word 22-23	176	16		VSS01607
		PSS01620	Word 24-25	192	16		VSS01607
		PSS01621	Word 26-27	208	16		VSS01607
		PSS01622	Word 28-29	224	16		VSS01607
		PSS01623	Word 30-31	240	16		VSS01607
		PSS01624	Word 32-33	256	16		VSS01607
		PSS01625	Word 34-35	272	16		VSS01607
		PSS01626	Word 36-37	288	16		VSS01607
		PSS01627	Word 38-39	304	16		VSS01607
		PSS01628	Word 40-41	320	16		VSS01607
		PSS01650	Word 42-43	336	16		VSS01607
		PSS01651	Word 44-45	352	16		VSS01607
ZSS17109	SIMB HRIC Stop Science						
ZSS17110	SIMB HRIC Detector On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17120	SIMB HRIC Diagnostic Mode	PSS01601	repetition time HRIC	0	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01601
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	16	16		VSS01602
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	32	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	43	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	48	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	59	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimensio	64	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	66	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	72	8		VSS08008
ZSS17121	SIMB HRIC Stop Diagnostic Mode						

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

3.1.4. STC TCs

Table 7 Limited report for STC TCs.

Name	Descr.	PARA NAME	Description	bit-position	bit length	Calibration	Range
ZSS17201	SIMB STC Power On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17202	SIMB STC SCIENCE	PSS01501	integration time	0	16	CSSP0001TC	
		PSS01629	repetition time STC	16	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01608
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	32	16		VSS01602
		PSS00301	number of windows	53	3		VSS03001
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	56	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	67	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	72	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	83	5		VSS00502
		PSS01103	start row pixel w2	88	11		VSS01101
		PSS00503	start strip pixel w2	99	5		VSS00501
		PSS01104	end row pixel w2	104	11		VSS01102
		PSS00504	end strip pixel w2	115	5		VSS00502
		PSS01105	start row pixel w3	120	11		VSS01101
		PSS00505	start strip pixel w3	131	5		VSS00501
		PSS01106	end row pixel w3	136	11		VSS01102
		PSS00506	end strip pixel w3	147	5		VSS00502
		PSS01107	start row pixel w4	152	11		VSS01102
		PSS00507	start strip pixel w4	163	5		VSS00501
		PSS01108	end row pixel w4	168	11		VSS01102
		PSS00508	end strip pixel w4	179	5		VSS00502
		PSS01109	start row pixel w5	184	11		VSS01101
		PSS00509	start strip pixel w5	195	5		VSS00501
		PSS01110	end row pixel w5	200	11		VSS01102
		PSS00510	end strip pixel w5	211	5		VSS00502
		PSS01111	start row pixel w6	216	11		VSS01101
		PSS00511	start strip pixel w6	227	5		VSS00501
		PSS01112	end row pixel w6	232	11		VSS01102
		PSS00512	end strip pixel w6	243	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimensio	248	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	250	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00602	Compression ratio w2	258	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00603	Compression ratio w3	266	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00604	Compression ratio w4	274	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00605	Compression ratio w5	282	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00606	Compression ratio w6	290	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	303	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	312	8		VSS08008
ZSS172B2	SIMB STC SCIENCE 1ms	PSS015B1	integration time 1ms	0	16	CSSP0002TC	VSS01618
		PSS01629	repetition time STC	16	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01608
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	32	16		VSS01602
		PSS00301	number of windows	53	3		VSS03001
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	56	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	67	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	72	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	83	5		VSS00502
		PSS01103	start row pixel w2	88	11		VSS01101

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		PSS00503	start strip pixel w2	99	5		VSS00501
		PSS01104	end row pixel w2	104	11		VSS01102
		PSS00504	end strip pixel w2	115	5		VSS00502
		PSS01105	start row pixel w3	120	11		VSS01101
		PSS00505	start strip pixel w3	131	5		VSS00501
		PSS01106	end row pixel w3	136	11		VSS01102
		PSS00506	end strip pixel w3	147	5		VSS00502
		PSS01107	start row pixel w4	152	11		VSS01102
		PSS00507	start strip pixel w4	163	5		VSS00501
		PSS01108	end row pixel w4	168	11		VSS01102
		PSS00508	end strip pixel w4	179	5		VSS00502
		PSS01109	start row pixel w5	184	11		VSS01101
		PSS00509	start strip pixel w5	195	5		VSS00501
		PSS01110	end row pixel w5	200	11		VSS01102
		PSS00510	end strip pixel w5	211	5		VSS00502
		PSS01111	start row pixel w6	216	11		VSS01101
		PSS00511	start strip pixel w6	227	5		VSS00501
		PSS01112	end row pixel w6	232	11		VSS01102
		PSS00512	end strip pixel w6	243	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimension	248	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	250	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00602	Compression ratio w2	258	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00603	Compression ratio w3	266	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00604	Compression ratio w4	274	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00605	Compression ratio w5	282	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00606	Compression ratio w6	290	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	303	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	312	8		VSS08008
ZSS17203	SIMB STC Thermal Control On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
		PSS01603	STC HRIC Temp set point	8	16		VSS01614
ZSS17204	SIMB STC Confirm Command						
ZSS17205	SIMB STC Upload parameters	PSS08010	STC param ID	0	8	CSST0013TC	VSS08009
		PSS01604	parameter value	8	32		
ZSS17206	SIMB STC Read Addr	PSS01607	PE STC Addr	0	16	CSST0012TC	VSS01605
ZSS17207	SIMB STC Write Addr	PSS01607	PE STC Addr	0	16	CSST0012TC	VSS01605
		PSS01606	Value to be write	16	16		
ZSS17208	SIMB STC Test PE	PSS01608	Word 0-1	0	16		VSS01607
		PSS01609	Word 2-3	16	16		VSS01607
		PSS01610	Word 4-5	32	16		VSS01607
		PSS01611	Word 6-7	48	16		VSS01607
		PSS01612	Word 8-9	64	16		VSS01607
		PSS01613	Word 10-11	80	16		VSS01607
		PSS01614	Word 12-13	96	16		VSS01607
		PSS01615	Word 14-15	112	16		VSS01607
		PSS01616	Word 16-17	128	16		VSS01607
		PSS01617	Word 18-19	144	16		VSS01607
		PSS01618	Word 20-21	160	16		VSS01607
		PSS01619	Word 22-23	176	16		VSS01607
		PSS01620	Word 24-25	192	16		VSS01607
		PSS01621	Word 26-27	208	16		VSS01607
		PSS01622	Word 28-29	224	16		VSS01607
		PSS01623	Word 30-31	240	16		VSS01607
		PSS01624	Word 32-33	256	16		VSS01607
		PSS01625	Word 34-35	272	16		VSS01607
		PSS01626	Word 36-37	288	16		VSS01607
		PSS01627	Word 38-39	304	16		VSS01607
		PSS01628	Word 40-41	320	16		VSS01607
		PSS01650	Word 42-43	336	16		VSS01607

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		PSS01651	Word 44-45	352	16		VSS01607
ZSS17209	SIMB STC Stop Science						
ZSS17210	SIMB STC Detector On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17220	SIMB STC Diagnostic Mode	PSS01629	repetition time STC	0	16	CSST0003TC	VSS01608
		PSS01602	NbrAcq	16	16		VSS01602
		PSS01101	start row pixel w1	32	11		VSS01101
		PSS00501	start strip pixel w1	43	5		VSS00501
		PSS01102	end row pixel w1	48	11		VSS01102
		PSS00502	end strip pixel w1	59	5		VSS00502
		PSS00205	Compression box dimensio	64	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	66	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	72	8		VSS08008
ZSS17221	SIMB STC Stop Diagnostic Mode						

3.1.5. VIHI TCs

Table 8 Limited report for VIHI TCs.

Name	Descr.	PARA NAME	Description	bit- pos ition	bit s len gth	Calibration	Range
ZSS17301	SIMB VIHI power On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17302	SIMB VIHI Science	PSS01630	VIHI integration time	0	16	CSST0007TC	
		PSS01631	VIHI Repetition time	16	16	CSST0003TC	VSS01609
		PSS01632	VIHI starting row pixel	32	16		VSS01610
		PSS01633	VIHI Starting columpixel	48	16		VSS01611
		PSS01634	VIHI End row pixel	64	16		VSS01610
		PSS01635	VIHI End colum pixel	80	16		VSS01611
		PSS00104	Dark subtraction status	96	1	CSST0003TC	
		PSS00105	Dark_Acquisition	97	1	CSST0011TC	
		PSS00207	Spatial binning VIHI	98	2	CSST0006TC	
		PSS00208	Binning sequence of frame	100	2	CSST0008TC	
		PSS00209	Spectral editing	102	2	CSST0007TC	
		PSS03207	VIHI Spare 32	104	32		
		PSS00205	Compression box dimension	136	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	138	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00106	Dark Macro	150	1	CSST0010TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	151	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	152	8		VSS08008
ZSS173B2	SIMB VIHI Science Minimum IT	PSS01631	VIHI Repetition time	16	16	CSST0003TC	VSS01609
		PSS01632	VIHI starting row pixel	32	16		VSS01610
		PSS01633	VIHI Starting columpixel	48	16		VSS01611
		PSS01634	VIHI End row pixel	64	16		VSS01610
		PSS01635	VIHI End colum pixel	80	16		VSS01611
		PSS00104	Dark subtraction status	96	1	CSST0003TC	
		PSS00105	Dark_Acquisition	97	1	CSST0011TC	
		PSS00207	Spatial binning VIHI	98	2	CSST0006TC	
		PSS00208	Binning sequence of frames	100	2	CSST0008TC	
		PSS00209	Spectral editing	102	2	CSST0007TC	
		PSS03207	VIHI Spare 32	104	32		
		PSS00205	Compression box dimension	136	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	138	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS00106	Dark Macro	150	1	CSST0010TC	
		PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode	151	1	CSST0014TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	152	8		VSS08008
ZSS17303	SIMB VIHI Thermal Control On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		PSS01636	VIHI Temp set point	8	16		VSS01614
ZSS17304	SIMB VIHI Confirm Command						
ZSS17305	SIMB VIHI Upload parameters	PSS08011	VIHI param ID	0	8	CSST0013TC	
		PSS01604	parameter value	8	32		
ZSS17306	SIMB VIHI Read Addr	PSS01637	PE VIHI Addr	0	16	CSST0015TC	VSS01613
ZSS17307	SIMB VIHI Write Addr	PSS01637	PE VIHI Addr	0	16	CSST0015TC	VSS01613
		PSS01606	Value to be write	16	16		
ZSS17308	SIMB VIHI Test PE	PSS01608	Word 0-1	0	16		VSS01607
		PSS01609	Word 2-3	16	16		VSS01607
		PSS01610	Word 4-5	32	16		VSS01607
		PSS01611	Word 6-7	48	16		VSS01607
		PSS01612	Word 8-9	64	16		VSS01607
		PSS01613	Word 10-11	80	16		VSS01607
		PSS01614	Word 12-13	96	16		VSS01607
		PSS01615	Word 14-15	112	16		VSS01607
		PSS01616	Word 16-17	128	16		VSS01607
		PSS01617	Word 18-19	144	16		VSS01607
		PSS01618	Word 20-21	160	16		VSS01607
		PSS01619	Word 22-23	176	16		VSS01607
		PSS01620	Word 24-25	192	16		VSS01607
		PSS01621	Word 26-27	208	16		VSS01607
		PSS01622	Word 28-29	224	16		VSS01607
ZSS17309	SIMB VIHI Stop Science						
ZSS17310	SIMB VIHI Detector On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
ZSS17311	SIMB VIHI_Shutter	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
		PSS01638	Shutter set point	8	16	CSSP0004TC	VSS01615
ZSS17312	SIMB VIHI Lamp On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
		PSS01639	Lamp set point	8	16	CSSP0004TC	VSS01617
ZSS17313	SIMB VIHI LED On/Off	PSS08006	On/off	0	8	CSST0001TC	
		PSS01640	LED current setpoint	8	16	CSSP0004TC	VSS01616
ZSS17320	SIMB VIHI Diagnostic Mode	PSS01631	VIHI Repetition time	0	16	CSSP0003TC	VSS01609
		PSS01632	VIHI starting row pixel	16	16		VSS01610
		PSS01633	VIHI Starting columpixel	32	16		VSS01611
		PSS01634	VIHI End row pixel	48	16		VSS01610
		PSS01635	VIHI End colum pixel	64	16		VSS01611
		PSS00205	Compression box dimension	80	2	CSST0005TC	VSS00202
		PSS00601	Compression ratio w1	82	6	CSST0009TC	
		PSS08008	Priority	88	8		VSS08008
ZSS17321	SIMB VIHI Stop Diagnostic Mode						

3.2. TC Range (VSS) definition

This section will list for each Range (VSS) of SIMBIO-SYS the limits defined.
A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 9 Link to the complete report of the TCs

DB2_1_ZSS_Ranges.xlsx	
-----------------------	---

Table 10 reports the description, the limits, the parameters and the TCs involved for each VSS.
All the Ranges modified with respect to the Database documentation (see [[RD. 2]]) are underlined in red.

The change log of the updates is reported in Table 10.

Table 10 Report log respect Version of MIB (see [RD. 1])

CPC_PRFR EF	PRF_DESCR	PRV_M INVAL	PRV_M AXVAL	Log Change
VSS00202	compression box dimension	1	3	Older Minimal Value was set to 0
VSS01601	repetition time HRIC	20	4000	Older Minimal Value was set to 2400
VSS01607	Words Test PE	0	FFFF	Older Word Test parameters had no a VSS range
VSS01608	repetition time STC	30	4000	Older Minimal Value was set to 2460
VSS01618	integration time 1ms	32768	53601	VSS was not present in older version.

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

Table 11 Limited report of the ranges (VSS) of the parameters TC. Res IDs identify the Ranges which were updated respect the last Database Report [RD. 2]

CPC_PRFPREF	PRF_DESCR	PRF_RADIX	PRV_MINVAL	PRV_MAXVAL	CDF_PNAME	CPC_DESCR	CCF_CNAME	CCF_DESCR
CSS06060TC	Memory ID	D	100	109	PSS06060	Memory ID	ZSS00602 ZSS00605 ZSS00609	Load Data in Memory Dump Memory Area Check Memory Area
VSS00201	binning factor	D	0	3	PSS00201 PSS00202 PSS00203 PSS00204	binning factor w1 binning factor w2 binning factor w3 binning factor w4	ZSS17102 ZSS171B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS00202	compression box dimension	D	1	3	PSS00205	Compression box dim.	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2 ZSS17302 ZSS17320 ZSS173B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms VIHI Science VIHI Diagnostic Mode VIHI Science Minimum IT
VSS00501	Start strip pixel	D	0	30	PSS00501 PSS00503 PSS00505 PSS00507 PSS00509 PSS00511	start strip pixel w1 start strip pixel w2 start strip pixel w3 start strip pixel w4 start strip pixel w5 start strip pixel w6	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS00502	end strip pixel	D	1	31	PSS00502 PSS00504 PSS00506 PSS00508 PSS00510 PSS00512	end strip pixel w1 end strip pixel w2 end strip pixel w3 end strip pixel w4 end strip pixel w5 end strip pixel w6	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE SIMB STC Diagnostic Mode SIMB STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01101	start row pixel	D	0	2047	PSS01101 PSS01103 PSS01105 PSS01109 PSS01111	start row pixel w1 start row pixel w2 start row pixel w3 start row pixel w5 start row pixel w6	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01102	end row Pixel	D	0	2047	PSS01102 PSS01104 PSS01106 PSS01107 PSS01108 PSS01110 PSS01112	end row pixel w1 end row pixel w2 end row pixel w3 start row pixel w4 end row pixel w4 end row pixel w5 end row pixel w6	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01601	repetition time HRIC	D	20	4000	PSS01601	repetition time HRIC	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01602	NbrAcq	D	1	65535	PSS01602	NbrAcq	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

							ZSS172B2	STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01604	PE HRIC Addr	D	0	9	PSS01605	PE HRIC Addr	ZSS17106 ZSS17107	HRIC Read Addr HRIC Write Addr
VSS01605	STC PE Address	D	0	9	PSS01607	PE STC Addr	ZSS17206 ZSS17207	STC Read Addr STC Write Addr
VSS01607	Words Test PE	H	0	FFFF	PSS01608 PSS01609 PSS01610 PSS01611 PSS01612 PSS01613 PSS01614 PSS01615 PSS01616 PSS01617 PSS01618 PSS01619 PSS01620 PSS01621 PSS01622 PSS01623 PSS01624 PSS01625 PSS01626 PSS01627 PSS01628 PSS01650 PSS01651	Word 0-1 Word 2-3 Word 4-5 Word 6-7 Word 8-9 Word 10-11 Word 12-13 Word 14-15 Word 16-17 Word 18-19 Word 20-21 Word 22-23 Word 24-25 Word 26-27 Word 28-29 Word 30-31 Word 32-33 Word 34-35 Word 36-37 Word 38-39 Word 40-41 Word 42-43 Word 44-45	ZSS17108 ZSS17208 ZSS17308	HRIC Test PE STC Test PE VIHI Test PE
VSS01608	repetition time STC	D	30	4000	PSS01629	repetition time STC	ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2	STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS01609	VIHI repetition time	D	8	2000	PSS01631	VIHI Repetition time	ZSS17302 ZSS17320 ZSS173B2	VIHI Science VIHI Diagnostic Mode VIHI Science Minimum IT
VSS01610	Row pixel VIHI	D	0	264	PSS01632 PSS01634	VIHI starting row pixel VIHI End row pixel	ZSS17302 ZSS17320 ZSS173B2 ZSS17320 ZSS173B2	VIHI Science VIHI Diagnostic Mode VIHI Science Minimum IT VIHI Diagnostic Mode VIHI Science Minimum IT
VSS01611	column pixel VIHI	D	0	264	PSS01633 PSS01635	VIHI Starting column pixel VIHI End column pixel	ZSS17302	VIHI Science
VSS01613	VIHI PE Address	D	0	6	PSS01637	PE VIHI Addr	ZSS17306 ZSS17307	VIHI Read Addr VIHI Write Addr
VSS01614	Temperature setpoint	H	0	4095	PSS01603 PSS01636	STC HRIC Temp set point VIHI Temp set point	ZSS17103 ZSS17203 ZSS17303	HRIC Thermal Control On/Off STC Thermal Control On/Off VIHI Thermal Control On/Off
VSS01615	Shutter current	D	0.00 01	0.251	PSS01638	Shutter set point	ZSS17311	VIHI_Shutter
VSS01616	LED Current	D	0.00 01	0.381	PSS01640	LED current setpoint	ZSS17313	VIHI LED On/Off
VSS01617	lamp Current	D	0.00 01	0.5233 5	PSS01639	Lamp set point	ZSS17312	VIHI Lamp On/Off
VSS01618	integration time 1ms	D	3276 8	53601	PSS015B1	integration time 1ms	ZSS171B2 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE 1ms
VSS03001	number of windows	D	1	6	PSS00301	number of windows	ZSS17102 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS172B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC SCIENCE 1ms

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

VSS08004	Collection Interval	D	1	65535	PSS08004	Collection Interval	ZSS00329	Define HK Report Collect Interval
VSS08005	PID	D	50	59	PSS08005	PID	ZSS02101 ZSS02102	Enable Start Science Transfer Disable Stop Science Transfer
VSS08007	HRIC param ID	D	1	5	PSS08007	HRIC param ID	ZSS17105	HRIC Upload parameters
VSS08008	high priority	D	0	255	PSS08008	Priority	ZSS17102 ZSS17120 ZSS171B2 ZSS17202 ZSS17220 ZSS172B2 ZSS17302 ZSS17320 ZSS173B2	HRIC SCIENCE HRIC Diagnostic Mode HRIC SCIENCE 1ms STC SCIENCE STC Diagnostic Mode STC SCIENCE 1ms VIHI Science VIHI Diagnostic Mode VIHI Science Minimum IT
VSS08009	STC param id	D	1	5	PSS08010	STC param ID	ZSS17205	STC Upload parameters

3.3. TC Calibrations

3.3.1. TC Numerical Calibrations (CSSP)

The section will list the Numerical Calibration of the parameters of the SIMBIOSYS TC. A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 12 Link to the complete report of the CSSP

DB2_2_TC Num Calibrations_ES.xlsx	
-----------------------------------	---

Table 13 reports for each CSSP: the description, the linear curves and the parameters involved. No Numerical Calibrations were updated respect the last Database Extraction (see [RD. 2])

Table 13 Limited report of the numerical calibration (CSSP) of the PSS parameters

CCA_NUMB R	CCA_DESCR	CPC _U NIT	CCS_XV ALS1	CCS_YVAL S1	CCS_XVAL S2	CCS_YVAL S2	PRF _U NIT	CPC_PNA ME	CPC_DESCR
CSSP0001T C	integration time 0.01ms	ms	0	0	314.5632	3276 7		PSS0150 1	integration time
CSSP0002T C	integration time 1ms	ms	314.88	3309 6	31456.32	6553 5	1m s	PSS015B 1	integration time 1ms

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

CSSP0003T C	science repetition time	5m s	20475	4095	5	1	5m s	PSS0160 1 PSS0162 9 PSS0163 1	repetition time HRIC repetition time STC VIHI Repetition time
CSSP0004T C	VIHI current setpoint	A	-0.009	0	0.52335	4095	A	PSS0163 8 PSS0163 9 PSS0164 0	Shutter set point Lamp set point LED current setpoint
CSSP0007T C	VIHI Integration Time	us	205.5	3	4489147. 5	6553 5		PSS0163 0	VIHI integration time

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

3.3.2. TC Textual Calibrations (CSSP)

The section will list the Textual Calibration of the parameters of the SIMBIOSYS TC. A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 14 Link to the complete report of the Text calibration

DB2_2_TC Text calibrations	
----------------------------	---

Table 15 report for each CSST: the description, the coding and, for each calibration the list of the PSS parameters involved.

No Textual Calibrations were updated respect the last Database Extraction (see [RD. 2])

Table 15 Limited report of the numerical calibration (CSST) of the PSS parameters

PAF_NUMBR	PAF_DESCR	PAS_ALV AL	PAS_ALTXT	CPC_PNA ME	CPC_DESCR
CSST0001TC	Off_On	0 1	Off On	PSS08006	On/off
CSST0002TC	SID	1 2 255 3 4	HRIC STC ALL VIHI ME	PSS08003	SID
CSST0003TC	Dark_Subtraction	0 1	No_Dark_Sub Dark_Sub	PSS00104	Dark subtraction status
CSST0004TC	binning_factor	0 1 2 3	No_Binning Binning_2x2 Binning_4x4 Binning_8x8	PSS00201 PSS00202 PSS00203 PSS00204	binning factor w1 binning factor w2 binning factor w3 binning factor w4
CSST0005TC	Compression Box Size	0 1 2 3	Unknow box 64x64 64x128 128x128	PSS00205	Compression box dimensio
CSST0006TC	VIHI Spatial Binning	0 1 2	No_Spatial_bin 2x_Spatial_bin 4x_Spatial_bin	PSS00207	Spatial binning VIHI
CSST0007TC	Spectral binning	0 1 2 3	No_Binning Spectral_Editing 2x_Spectral_bin 4x_Spectral_bin	PSS00209	Spectral editing
CSST0008TC	Frame binning	0 1	No_Binning 2frame_binning	PSS00208	Binning sequence of fram

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		2	4frame_binning		
CSST0009TC	Compression ratio	0	Bit_Packing	PSS00601	Compression ratio w1
		1	Lossless	PSS00602	Compression ratio w2
		10	Wavelet_IBR10	PSS00603	Compression ratio w3
		11	Wavelet_IBR11	PSS00604	Compression ratio w4
		12	Wavelet_IBR12	PSS00605	Compression ratio w5
		13	Wavelet_IBR13	PSS00606	Compression ratio w6
		14	Wavelet_IBR14		
		15	Wavelet_IBR15		
		16	Wavelet_IBR16		
		17	Wavelet_IBR17		
		18	Wavelet_IBR18		
		19	Wavelet_IBR19		
		2	Wavelet_IBR2		
		20	Wavelet_IBR20		
		21	Wavelet_IBR21		
		22	Wavelet_IBR22		
		23	Wavelet_IBR23		
		24	Wavelet_IBR24		
		25	Wavelet_IBR25		
		26	Wavelet_IBR26		
		27	Wavelet_IBR27		
		28	Wavelet_IBR28		
		29	Wavelet_IBR29		
		3	Wavelet_IBR3		
		30	Wavelet_IBR30		
		31	Wavelet_IBR31		
		32	Wavelet_IBR32		
		33	Wavelet_IBR33		
		34	Wavelet_IBR34		
		35	Wavelet_IBR35		
		36	Wavelet_IBR36		
		37	Wavelet_IBR37		
		38	Wavelet_IBR38		
		39	Wavelet_IBR39		
		4	Wavelet_IBR4		
		40	Wavelet_IBR40		
		41	Wavelet_IBR41		
		42	Wavelet_IBR42		
		43	Wavelet_IBR43		
		44	Wavelet_IBR44		
		45	Wavelet_IBR45		
		46	Wavelet_IBR46		
		47	Wavelet_IBR47		
		48	Wavelet_IBR48		
		49	Wavelet_IBR49		
		5	Wavelet_IBR5		
		50	Wavelet_IBR50		
		51	Wavelet_IBR51		
		52	Wavelet_IBR52		
		53	Wavelet_IBR53		
		54	Wavelet_IBR54		
		55	Wavelet_IBR55		
		56	Wavelet_IBR56		
		57	Wavelet_IBR57		
		58	Wavelet_IBR58		
		59	Wavelet_IBR59		
		6	Wavelet_IBR6		

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		60	Wavelet_IBR60		
		61	Wavelet_IBR61		
		62	Wavelet_IBR62		
		63	Wavelet_IBR63		
		7	Wavelet_IBR7		
		8	Wavelet_IBR8		
		9	Wavelet_IBR9		
CSST0010TC	Dark Macro	0	No_Dark_Macro	PSS00106	Dark Macro
		1	Dark_Macro		
CSST0011TC	Dark_Acquisition	0	No_Dark_acq	PSS00105	Dark_Acquisition
		1	Dark_acq		
CSST0012TC	HRIC/STC Register Addr	0	TEST_PATTERN_ADD	PSS01605	PE HRIC Addr
		1	ROIC1_ADD	PSS01607	PE STC Addr
		2	ROIC2_ADD		
		3	ROIC_FREQ		
		4	DAC_VRSTUC		
		5	DAC_VGUARD		
		6	ENABLE_PROT		
		7	RESET_PROT_FLAG		
		8	SET_PROT_FLAG		
		9	PWM_RATIO_ADDR		
CSST0013TC	PE TEC Param ID	1	N_P for PID TEC	PSS08007	HRIC param ID
		2	N_I for PID TEC	PSS08010	STC param ID
		3	N_E for PID TEC	PSS08011	VIHI param ID
		4	N_SS		
		5	B_Start		
CSST0014TC	PE MODE	0	Nominal_Mode	PSS00101	LS bit1 PE mode
		1	Test_Mode		
CSST0015TC	VIHI PE Address	0	TEST PATTERN ADD	PSS01637	PE VIHI Addr
		1	ROIC1 ADDR		
		2	ROIC2 ADDR		
		3	ROIC3 ADDR		
		4	VDET COM		
		5	VDET ADJ		
		6	PWM RATIO ADDR		
CSST6060TC	Memory ID	100	RAM	PSS06060	Memory ID
		101	EEPROM		
		102	PROM		
		103	REGISTER		
		104	ONCHIP_RAM		
		105	FPGA_CPCU		
		106	IO_HRIC		
		107	IO_STC		
		108	IO_VIHI		
		109	DPRAM		

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

4. TM Organization

Next sections will report the current ESOC database for what concern the TM of SIMBIO-SYS (see Section), including:

- the calibration, both in the case of numeric (see section 4.2.1) and textual (see section 4.2.2)

4.1. TM Definition

This report will list for each TM of SIMBIOSYS the parameters involved.
A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 16 Link to the complete report of the TMs

DB1_4_Analog TM (calibrated or not).xlsx	
--	--

The Table 17 reports for each TM: the description, the calibration of the TM (see 4.2) connected.

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

Table 17 Limited report of the TM reporting for each NSS the ID, the description and the Calibration ID.

(a)			(b)		
NSS ID	Description	CSSP ID	NSS ID	Description	CSSP ID
NSS01073	Spare 1		NSS31051	VIHI TEC Current	0036TM
NSS01074	Spare 2		NSS31062	Temperature Spectrometer	0032TM
NSS01075	Spare 3		NSS31063	Temperature Calib Unit	0032TM
NSS01076	Spare 4		NSS31070	Pixel 1	
NSS06001	Start Address		NSS31071	Pixel 2	
NSS06002	Length		NSS31072	Pixel 3	
NSS06003	Data		NSS32401	VIHI AcquisitionTime-CUC	
NSS06004	Memory Checksum		NSS42401	ME Acquisition Time- CUC	
NSS08000	TC Packet ID		NSS48020	temperature on ME board	0001TM
NSS08001	Packet Sequence Control		NSS48021	temp DCDC Conv	0001TM
NSS08002	FID		NSS48022	Voltage at 3.3V	0002TM
NSS08010	TC Packet Type		NSS48023	Voltage at 5V	0002TM
NSS08011	TC Packet Subtype		NSS48024	ME/CPCU status	
NSS08012	Received Checksum		NSS48025	ME/CU HRIC status	
NSS08013	Computed Checksum		NSS48026	ME/CU STC status	
NSS08030	Id (from 1) incons par		NSS48027	ME/CU VIHI status	
NSS08031	Received param val		NSS49001	SIMB BSW Version	
NSS08032	Min expected value		NSS49005	AT1 Add of First error	
NSS08033	Max expected value		NSS49008	AT2 Addr of first error	
NSS08050	Computed CRC in EEPROM		NSS49011	AT3 Addr of first error	
NSS08051	Computed CRC in RAM		NSS49014	AT4 Addr of first error	
NSS08052	EEPROM nbr of page fail		NSS49017	AT5 Addr of first error	
NSS08053	Fisrt EEPROM adr in fail		NSS50002	User trap number	
NSS08054	Received CRC		NSS50003	PC of calling function	
NSS08055	Computed CRC		NSS50004	PC of called function	
NSS08060	Packet Sourceld received		NSS51000	SpW Status Register	
NSS08501	Event ID 5_1		NSS51001	SpW CODEC Status Reg	
NSS08502	Event ID 5_2		NSS51002	SpW RxVC Status Reg 0	
NSS08503	Event ID 5_3		NSS51003	SpW RxVC Interrupt Reg0	
NSS08504	Event ID 5_4		NSS51004	SpW TxVC Status Reg1	
NSS11020	HRIC Commanded TEC Tref		NSS51005	SpW TxVC Interrupt Reg1	
NSS11021	HRIC Commanded TEC N_P		NSS51006	SpW Link Int Status Reg	
NSS11022	HRIC Commanded TEC N_I		NSS51007	SpW 1st Failing Pack Reg	
NSS11023	HRIC Commanded TEC N_E		NSSD1124	HRIC Commanded TEC N_SS	
NSS11031	HRIC Contents of PE Addr		NSSD2124	STC Commanded TEC N_SS	
NSS11040	HRIC Temperature FPA1	0010TM	NSSD3124	VIHI Commanded TEC N_SS	
NSS11041	HRIC Temperature FPA2	0011TM	NSSD3161	Commanded Current	
NSS11042	HRIC Temperature PE	0012TM	NSSD3165	Measured current	0037TM
NSS11043	HRIC Temp Tele1	0013TM	NSSD4904	SIMB AT1 Number of error	
NSS11044	HRIC Temp Tele2	0014TM	NSSD4907	AT2 Number of error	

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

NSS11050	HRIC PE 3.3V Measured	0015TM	NSSD4910	AT3 Number of error	
NSS11051	HRIC TEC Current	0016TM	NSSD4913	AT4 Number of error	
NSS12401	HRIC AcquisitionTime-CUC		NSSD4916	AT5 Number of error	
NSS21020	STC Commanded TEC Tref		NSSD9020	SpW register error	
NSS21021	STC Commanded TEC N_P		NSSD9031	Num errors between 2 FR	
NSS21022	STC Commanded TEC N_I		NSSD9032	Total num detected error	
NSS21023	STC Commanded TEC N_E		NSSG1101	HRIC PE Status	
NSS21031	STC Contents of PE Addr		NSSG1102	HRIC N_SS	
NSS21040	STC Temperature FPA1	0020TM	NSSG2101	STC PE Status	
NSS21041	STC Temperature FPA2	0021TM	NSSG2102	STC N_SS	
NSS21042	STC Temperature PE	0022TM	NSSG3101	VIHI PE Status	
NSS21043	STC Temp channel fw	0023TM	NSSG3102	VIHI N_SS	
NSS21044	STC Temp Channel bw	0024TM	NSSG3103	VIHI Commanded Current	
NSS21050	STC PE 3.3V Measured	0025TM	NSSG3104	VIHI Measured Current	
NSS21051	STC TEC Current	0026TM	NSSG4100	Simbio-Sys Cur status	
NSS22401	STC AcquisitionTime-CUC		NSSG4110	Simbio-Sys Prev Status	
NSS31020	VIHI Commanded TEC Tref		NSSG4200	CU Channel SpW Error	
NSS31021	VIHI Commanded TEC N_P		NSSG4210	SpW num errors in 2 reqs	
NSS31022	VIHI Commanded TEC N_I		NSSG4301	RAM Autotest1	
NSS31023	VIHI Commanded TEC N_E		NSSG4302	RAM Autotest2	
NSS31031	VIHI Contents of PE Addr		NSSG4303	RAM Autotest3	
NSS31040	VIHI Temperature FPA1	0030TM	NSSG4304	RAM Autotest4	
NSS31041	VIHI Temperature FPA2	0031TM	NSSG4305	RAM Autotest5	
NSS31042	VIHI Temperature PE	0032TM	NSSG4306	Channel not Operative	
NSS31050	VIHI PE 3.3V Measured	0035TM			

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

4.2. TM Calibration

4.2.1. TM Numerical Calibration (CSSP)

The report will list the Numerical Calibration of the SIMBIOSYS TM.
A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 18 Link to the complete report of the Numerical calibration

DB2_4_TM Num calibration	
--------------------------	--

Table 19 reports for each CSSP, the linear definition and, for each calibration the list of the TM involved.

Table 19 Limited report of the numerical calibration (CSSP) of the TM parameters

CAF_NUMBR	CAP_YVAL 1	CAP_XVAL 2	CAP_YVAL2	PCF_NAME	PCF_DESCR
CSSP0001TM	0	4095	600	NSS48020 NSS48021	temperature on ME board temp DCDC Conv
CSSP0002TM	0	4096	6	NSS48022 NSS48023	Voltage at 3.3V Voltage at 5V
CSSP0010TM	516.88	4095	152.875	NSS11040	HRIC Temperature FPA1
CSSP0011TM	515.731	4095	153.9136	NSS11041	HRIC Temperature FPA2
CSSP0012TM	20.26384	4095	462.1143	NSS11042	HRIC Temperature PE
CSSP0013TM	20.28482	4095	462.8151	NSS11043	HRIC Temp Tele1
CSSP0014TM	20.00033	4095	462.6412	NSS11044	HRIC Temp Tele2
CSSP0015TM	0	4095	3.850762	NSS11050	HRIC PE 3.3V Measured
CSSP0016TM	-0.8326	4095	2.069076	NSS11051	HRIC TEC Current
CSSP0020TM	517.204	4095	154.2171	NSS21040	STC Temperature FPA1
CSSP0021TM	520.437	4095	153.7924	NSS21041	STC Temperature FPA2
CSSP0022TM	20.26384	4095	462.9907	NSS21042	STC Temperature PE
CSSP0023TM	20.28637	4095	462.8494	NSS21043	STC Temp channel fw
CSSP0024TM	20.08158	4095	462.2843	NSS21044	STC Temp Channel bw
CSSP0025TM	0	4095	3.852257	NSS21050	STC PE 3.3V Measured
CSSP0026TM	-0.83811	4095	2.082772	NSS21051	STC TEC Current
CSSP0030TM	336.8054	4095	194.95501	NSS31040	VIHI Temperature FPA1
CSSP0031TM	340.9103	4095	197.01306	NSS31041	VIHI Temperature FPA2
CSSP0032TM	192.25	4095	360.145	NSS31042 NSS31062 NSS31063	VIHI Temperature PE Temperature Spectrometer Temperature Calib Unit
CSSP0035TM	0	4095	3.56265	NSS31050	VIHI PE 3.3V Measured
CSSP0036TM	-5E-4	4095	1.18705	NSS31051	VIHI TEC Current
CSSP0037TM	-0.008	4095	0.52435	NSSD3165	Measured current

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

4.2.2. Textual Calibrations (CSST)

The report will list the Textual Calibration of the SIMBIOSYS TM. A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 20 Link to the complete report of the Text calibration

DB2_3 TM Text calibrations	
----------------------------	---

Table 21 reports for each CSST: the description, the coding and, for each calibration the list of the TM involved.

No Textual Calibrations were updated with respect the last Database Extraction (see [RD. 2]).

Table 21 Limited report of the numerical calibration (CSST) of the TM parameters

TXF_NUMBR	TXF_DESCR	Ex pr1 00 7	Expr1 008	TXP_ALTXT	PCF_NAME	PCF_DESCR
CAAT0001TM	Off_On	0 1	0 1	Off On	NSSD1100 NSSD1101 NSSD1126 NSSD2100 NSSD2101 NSSD2126 NSSD3100 NSSD3101 NSSD3105 NSSD3106 NSSD3107 NSSD3126	HRICCommanded detec stat HRICCommanded TEC stat HRIC Anti wind-up status STC Commanded detec stat STC Commanded TEC stat STC Anti wind-up status VIHICommanded detec stat VIHICommanded TEC stat Lamp Commanded Status LED Commanded Status Dark Commanded Status VIHI Anti wind-up status
CAAT0037TM	Open_Closed	0 1	0 1	Open Closed	NSSD3104	Shutter commanded status
CSST1000TM	Channel Test Mode	0 1	0 1	No Test Mode Test Mode	NSSD1102 NSSD2102 NSSD3102	HRIC Commanded test mode STC Commanded test mode VIHI Commanded test mode
CSST1001TM	Dark Subtraction status	0 1	0 1	dark not subtr dark subtrac	NSSD3108	Dark Sub Commanded Stat
CSST1010TM	Last Event	0 1 2 4 8 16 65	0 1 2 4 8 16 65	NO ERROR TC Acq Sc rej TC Wrong Id TC length Nok TC EOP not rec TC Timer Ovrfr TC SpW Disc Er	NSS11010 NSS21010 NSS31010	HRIC Last Event STC Last Event VIHI Last Event

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		66	66	TC SpW Par Er		
		68	68	TC SpW Esc Er		
		72	72	TC SpW Cred Er		
		80	80	TC SpW N_Ch Er		
		19				
		3	193	TM SpW Disc Er		
		19				
		4	194	TM SpW Par Er		
		19				
		6	196	TM SpW Esc Er		
		20				
		0	200	TM SpW Cred Er		
		20				
		8	208	TM SpW N_Ch Er		
CSST1020TM	Anti wind-up method	0	0	P-only	NSSD1125	HRIC Anti wind-up method
		1	1	Ramp	NSSD2125	STC Anti wind-up method
					NSSD3125	VIHI Anti wind-up method
CSST1030TM	HRIC/ STC Address	0	0	Test Pattern	NSS11030	HRIC PE Address
		1	1	ROIC1 Addr	NSS21030	STC PE Address
		2	2	ROIC2 Addr		
		3	3	ROIC Freq		
		4	4	DAC vRstUc		
		5	5	DAC_vGuard		
		6	6	ENABLE PROT		
		7	7	RESET PROT F		
		8	8	SET PROT FLAG		
		9	9	PWM RATIO ADDR		
			6553			
		10	5	Invalid Addr		
CSST1031TM	VIHI Address	0	0	Test Pattern	NSS31030	VIHI PE Address
		1	1	ROIC1 Addr		
		2	2	ROIC2 Addr		
		3	3	ROIC3 Addr		
		4	4	VDET_COM		
		5	5	VDET_ADJ		
		6	6	PWM RATIO ADDR		
			6553			
		7	5	Invalid Address		
CSST1040TM	Commanded VIHI Device Id	0	0	Device Unknown	NSSD3160	Commanded VIHI device
		1	1	Shutter	NSSD3164	Measured VIHI Device
		2	2	LED		
		3	3	Device Unknown		
		4	4	Lamp		
		5	7	Device Unknown		
CSST1069TM	HK SID	1	1	HRIC	NSS18004	SID of HRIC Housekeeping
		2	2	STC	NSS28005	SID of STC Housekeeping
		3	3	VIHI	NSS38006	SID of VIHI Housekeeping
		4	4	ME	NSS48003	SID of ME Housekeeping
					NSS52000	Structure ID
CSST3000TM	RAM Check Status	0	0	OK	NSSD4903	SIMB Status Auto-Test1
		1	1	Failed	NSSD4906	Status of Autotest2
					NSSD4909	Status of Autotest3
					NSSD4912	Status of Autotest4
					NSSD4915	Status of Autotest5
CSST3001TM	CPCU FPGA Status	0	0	Ok	NSS49002	SIMB Status FPGA CPCU
		1	1	Failed		

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

		2	6553 5	Value Not Vali		
CSST6060TM	Memory ID	10 0 10 1 10 2 10 3 10 4 10 5 10 6 10 7 10 8 10 9	100 101 102 103 104 105 106 107 108 109	RAM EEPROM PROM REGISTER ONCHIP_RAM FPGA_CPCU IO_HRIC IO_STC IO_VIHI DPRAM	NSS06000	MemoryID
CSST8000TM	Channel SW Status	0 1 2 3 4 5	0 1 2 3 4 5	NA Channel Off Channel Stby Channel scien Chan diag Off Chan diag Sci	NSSD4401 NSSD4402 NSSD4403 NSSD4411 NSSD4412 NSSD4413	VIHI Cur Status STC Cur Status HRIC Cur Status VIHI Prev Status STC Prev Status HRIC Prev Status
CSST8001TM	ME SW Status	0 1 2 3 4	0 1 2 3 4	Not Applicable Boot SW Sby Boot SW Maint App SW Started App ME Diag	NSSD4404 NSSD4414	ME SW Cur Status ME SW Prev Status
CSST8010TM	Channel Id	1 2 3	1 2 3	HRIC STC VIHI	NSSD9010 NSSD9030 NSSD9040	Id Channel SpW error Channel Id Not Operative Channel Id
CSST8020TM	filler	0 1	0 63	0 Not Valid	NSSD9041	filler
CSST8030TM	SpW Time code lost status	0 1	0 1	SpWTimeCodeOK SpWTimCodeLost	NSS48030	SpW Time code lost stat

	Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
	Date	29/06/2022		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page			

4.3. TM Out of Limits

The report will list the Soft and Hard OOL of the SIMBIO-SYS TM.
A more detailed table can be downloaded at the following link.

Table 22 Link to the complete report of the Text calibration

DB4 TM OOL	
------------	---

Following tables (from Table 23 to Table 27) reports for each NSS: the description, the Soft OOL , the Hard out of limits (low and high in both the cases) and where present their variation as function of other conditions (NSSD). As example NSS11044 (Temp Tele2) has three ranges of OOLs depending on the value assumed by NSSD1100 and NSSS0001.

The subsequent tables report the same limits range for S/C Telemetries connected to SIMBIO-SYS.

Table 23 Out of limits and their variation conditions for all the TMs of HRIC, Chanel of SIMBIO-SYS.

PCF NAME	PCF DESCR	SOFT OCP		HARD OCP		CONDITION		
		LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	PARAM	DESCR	VAL
NSS11010	Last Event			0		NSSSZ002	SIMBIO HRIC ON	1
NSS11040	Temp FPA1	208	328	203	333	NSSD1100	Commanded detec stat	0
				263	303	NSSD1100	Commanded detec stat	1
NSS11041	Temp FPA2			263	303	NSSD1100	Commanded detec stat	1
		208	328	203	333	NSSD1100	Commanded detec stat	0
NSS11042	Temp PE	260	303	258	348			
NSS11043	Temp Tele1	268	338					
NSS11044	Temp Tele2	238	318	233	323	NSSD1100	Commanded detec stat	0
		268	286	263	291	NSSS0001	condition for NSS11044	1
		268	303	263	308	NSSS0001	condition for NSS11044	0
NSS11050	PE 3.3V Measured	3.15	3.45	3	3.6			
NSS11051	TEC Current	-0.05	0.8	-0.05	1.1			

Table 24 Out of limits and their variation conditions for all the TMs of STC, Chanel of SIMBIO-SYS.

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

PCF NAME	PCF DESCR	SOFT OCP		HARD OCP		CONDITION		
		LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	PARAM	DESCR	VAL
NSS21010	Last Event			0		NSSSZ003	SIMBIO STC ON	1
NSS21040	Temp FPA1	208	328	203	333	NSSD2100	Commanded detec stat	0
				263	303	NSSD2100	Commanded detec stat	1
NSS21041	Temp FPA2	208	328	203	333	NSSD2100	Commanded detec stat	0
				263	303	NSSD2100	Commanded detec stat	1
NSS21042	Temp PE	260	303	258	348			
NSS21043	Temp Ch FW	238	318	233	323	NSSD2100	Commanded detec stat	0
		268	286	263	291	NSSS0002	condition for NSS21043	1
		268	303	263	308	NSSS0002	condition for NSS21043	0
NSS21044	Temp Ch BW	263	305					
NSS21050	PE 3.3V Measured	3.15	3.45	3	3.6			
NSS21051	TEC Current	-0.05	0.8	-0.05	1.1			

Table 25 Out of limits and their variation conditions for all the TMs of VIHI Channel of SIMBIO-SYS.

PCF NAME	PCF DESCR	SOFT OCP		HARD OCP		CONDITION		
		LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	PARAM	DESCR	VAL
NSS31010	Last Event			0		NSSSZ004	SIMBIO VIHI ON	1
NSS31040	Temp FPA1	208	328	203	333	NSSD3100	Commanded detec stat	0
				210	303	NSSD3100	Commanded detec stat	1
NSS31041	Temp FPA2	208	328	203	333	NSSD3100	Commanded detec stat	0
				210	303	NSSD3100	Commanded detec stat	1
NSS31042	Temp PE	260	303	258	348			
NSS31050	PE 3.3V Measured	3.15	3.45	3	3.56			
NSS31051	TEC Current	-0.0005	1.15	-0.0005	1.185			

Table 26 Out of limits and their variation conditions for all the other TMs of SIMBIO-SYS.

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

PCF NAME	PCF DESCR	SOFT OCP		HARD OCP		CONDITION		
		LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	PARAM	DESCR	VAL
NSS31062	Temp Spectrometer	215	308	210	313	NSSD3100	Commanded detec Stat	0
		218	253	213	258	NSSS0003	condition for NSS31062	1
		218	303	213	308	NSSS0003	condition for NSS31062	0
NSS31063	Temp Calib Unit	263	310					
NSS48020	Temp on ME board			228.15	348.15			
NSS48021	Temp DCDC Conv			228.15	348.15			
NSS48022	Voltage at 3.3V	3.15	3.45	3	3.601			
NSS48023	Voltage at 5V	4.75	5.25	4.5	5.5			
NSSD3165	Measured current	0.1	0.38	0	0.42	NSSD3106	LED Commanded Status	1
		0.1	0.45	0	0.5	NSSD3105	Lamp Commanded Status	1
		0.07	0.2	0	0.35	NSSD3104	Shutter commanded status	1

Table 27 Out of limits and their variation conditions for all the S/C TM connected to SIMBIO-SYS.

PCF NAME	PCF DESCR	SOFT OCP		HARD OCP		CONDITION		
		LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	PARAM	DESCR	VAL
NRUD1003	MPO-TEMP-18-A-SIMB-STC	-10	13	-15	14	NSSSZ001	SIMBIO ME ON	1
NRUD2003	MPO-TEMP-18-B-SIMB-STC	-10	13	-15	14	NSSSZ001	SIMBIO ME ON	1
NRUD2079	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRIC-CF	-7	11	-10	14	NSSSZ002	SIMBIO HRIC ON	1
NRUD2083	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRIC-PE	-10	13	-15	14	NSSSZ002	SIMBIO HRIC ON	1
NRUD2087	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF	-7	11	-10	14	NSSSZ003	SIMBIO STC ON	1
NRUD2091	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-VIHI-CF	-60	-19.5	-63	-16.5	NSSSZ004	SIMBIO VIHI ON	1
NRUD3082	MPO-TEMP-SIMB-TM-HRICBAF	-40	90			NRUS000A	IO A On	1
NRUD6079	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRICTRP	-7	11	-10	14	NSSSZ002	SIMBIO HRIC ON	1
NRUD6083	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-ME	-17	47	-20	50	NSSSZ001	SIMBIO ME ON	1
NRUD6083	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-ME	-27	47	-40	50	NSSSZ001	SIMBIO ME ON	0
NRUD6087	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-PE	-10	13	-15	14	NSSSZ003	SIMBIO STC ON	1

Document	BC-SIM-TN-021 SIMBIO-SYS TM-TC database completeness status		
Date	29/06/2022		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page			

NRUD6091	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STCTRP	-7	11	-10	14	NSSSZ003	SIMBIO STC ON	1
NRUD8003	MPO-TEMP-18-C-SIMB-STC	-10	13	-15	14	NSSSZ001	SIMBIO ME ON	1
NRUD8082	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-VIHIBAF	-40	90			NRUS000B	IO B On	1
NRUD1022	MPO-TEMP-19-A-VIHI	-60	-19.5	-63	-16.5	NSSSZ004	SIMBIO VIHI ON	1
NRUD2022	MPO-TEMP-19-B-VIHI	-60	-19.5	-63	-16.5	NSSSZ004	SIMBIO VIHI ON	1
NRUD8022	MPO-TEMP-19-C-VIHI	-60	-19.5	-63	-16.5	NSSSZ004	SIMBIO VIHI ON	1